

Physicochemical Properties of Artificial Clay Mixtures

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The mixtures of clay minerals may reflect the properties of the individual components. But the presence of amorphous material, viz. hydrous alumina, may modify the physicochemical properties of clays^{1,2}, either occurring as an external coating on the layer silicates or by occupying the interlayer spaces of crystalline clay minerals. In the present discussion, cation-exchange capacities and swelling characteristics of H-bentonite, H-kaolinite, alumina and their artificial binary mixtures have been described.

Results and Discussion

The cation-exchange capacity of the binary mixtures of bentonite and kaolinite shows additivity with the composition (Fig. 1). But a slight deviation from additivity is observed in the case of bentonite-alumina mixtures. The intake of water by bentonite and the mixtures containing higher proportion of bentonite takes place at a relatively slow rate (Table 1). But the intake of water by kaolinite and alumina takes place rather rapidly. In the case of toluene intake, the equilibrium between clays or their binary mixtures and toluene is established fast. The total intake of water includes water sorbed (i) by the capillary pores, (ii) on the surfaces and round the edges of the discrete particles and (iii) in between the unit-cell layers of the expanding lattice type of minerals. In kaolinite and alumina, the sorption of water is due only to the first two causes. So the equilibrium between water and kaolinite or alumina is established rather quickly. As more energy is required for

definite orientation of the water molecules between the unit-cells of bentonite, the sorption of water takes place slowly.

TABLE 1-RATES OF WATER INTAKE AND TOLUENE INTAKE BY CLAY SAMPLES AND THEIR BINARY MIXTURES

Sample (Composition)	Time h	Water intake ml/g sample	Toluene intake ml/g sample
Bentonite (B)	0.25	2.83	1.62
	0.5	2.85	1.65
	1.0	2.98	1.67
	2.0	3.09	1.68
	3.0	3.14	1.69
	4.0	3.16	1.70
Kaolinite (K)	0.25	1.60	2.52
	0.5	1.62	2.55
	1.0	1.64	2.60
	2.0	1.65	2.65
	3.0	1.65	2.67
	4.0	1.65	2.67
Alumina (A)	0.25	1.00	1.89
	0.5	1.01	1.92
	1.0	1.02	1.96
	2.0	1.02	1.98
	3.0	1.02	2.00
Mixture :			
Mix. I (B : K = 2 : 1)	0.25	2.44	1.82
	0.5	2.46	1.86
	1.0	2.54	1.91
	2.0	2.58	1.93
	3.0	2.61	1.95
	4.0	2.63	1.96
Mix. II (B : K = 1 : 2)	0.25	2.11	1.94
	0.5	2.14	2.01
	1.0	2.18	2.20
	2.0	2.20	2.24
	3.0	2.22	2.27
	4.0	2.24	2.29
Mix. III (B : A = 2 : 1)	0.25	2.52	1.71
	0.5	2.56	1.74
	1.0	2.59	1.82
	2.0	2.63	1.85
	3.0	2.65	1.86
	4.0	2.66	1.87
	5.0	2.77	1.87

Fig. 1. Additivity of CEC of binary mixtures of clays as determined by NBaCl_2 and Ba(OH)_2 : (1) bentonite, kaolinite and their mixtures, (2) bentonite, alumina and their mixtures.

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Table -1 (contd)

Mix. IV (B : A = 1 : 2)	0.25	1.97	2.05
	0.5	2.00	2.10
	1.0	2.01	2.16
	2.0	2.02	2.18
	3.0	2.03	2.19

The surface tension of toluene is lower than water. So toluene may get into those micropores which are not accessible to water. It is evident from Table 1 that about 80% of the total sorption by bentonite and its mixtures with kaolinite and alumina takes place within an interval of about 30 min, whereas in kaolinite and alumina the total sorption is nearly complete within 15 min. It may be concluded that about 80% of the sorbed water must be taken up at the expense of the least amount of energy and this fraction may be correlated with the intermicellar swelling of the clay minerals and the rest of the sorption may be due to intramicellar swelling and for this purpose more energy, and also more time is required for definite orientation of water molecules.

The linear relationship between the cation-exchange capacity and the total intake of water and toluene of binary clay mixtures of bentonite and kaolinite with their composition suggests that the component clays retain more or less their individual characteristics. The additive nature of the cation-exchange capacity and total intake of water and toluene of the binary mixture may be used to ascertain the proportion of each in the mixture. But deviation from the additivity is observed in the cation-exchange capacity and total intake of water and toluene of the mixtures of bentonite and alumina. These deviation may be due to alumina, either occurring as an external coating of the layer silicates, or by way of occupying the interlayer spaces of crystalline clay minerals. Thus the presence of amorphous material in clays may modify or change the physicochemical properties of the clays. Barnhisel observed that interlayering of hydroxy aluminium in expanding clays reduces the cation-exchange capacity¹. Davey and Low²

observed a marked effect on viscosity and water tension due to the effect of freshly precipitated hydrous aluminium oxide on Na-saturated Wyoming bentonite.

Experimental

Bentonite and kaolinite clay fractions ($< 2 \mu\text{m}$) were isolated and collected by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation. The sample was then freed from residual organic matter by H_2O_2 treatment while the iron oxides were removed by citrate-bicarbonate-dithionite method³. It was converted to the H-form by H-resin (Amberlite IR-120) treatment. Binary mixtures of different weight ratios of bentonite and kaolinite and bentonite and alumina were prepared by adding one sol (1%) into the other at room temperature with continuous shaking. The mixtures were allowed to equilibrate with occasional shaking for more than one month.

The cation exchange capacity was determined potentiometrically with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in presence of BaCl_2 . N_2 -gas was passed through the solution to remove the dissolved CO_2 and the measurement was made in an N_2 -atmosphere.

The total intake of water and toluene per g of the clay samples was determined in the modified apparatus of Baver⁴. The bottom of a pyrex glass crucible was specially designed and joined with a straight-graduated tube of fine bore through standard joint. The vacuum-dried sample was quickly placed on the base of the crucible. The crucible was covered with a lid of ground-glass ending in a fine capillary. The flow of liquid through the graduated tube led to the index of the volume of liquid taken up by the sample. The results were expressed in ml/g after blank correction for the same equilibrium period.

References

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